

Magnetic Field Flying Vehicle

Technology

Description

Earth Magnetic Field can be used as a magnet to propel special flying vehicles that use this field to generate thrust so they can fly above Earth till this field reduces its power. The machine doesn't use any kind of fuel and it stays levitated and moves using earth as a magnet for its maneuvers.

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